

THE THEME OF IMMORTALITY AND RESURRECTION OF THE SOUL

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7991949>

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Annotation.

The article is devoted to the study of the theme of immortality and the resurrection of souls in the work of M. Bulgakov "The Master and Margarita". Assess Woland's actions and answer the question: "Does Woland do bad deeds or does he act in justice?"

Key words.

philosophy, psychology, death, bottomlessness, meaning of life, unity, devil, Yershalaim, MASSOLIT, suffering, renunciation, reunion, tranquility, immortality, hemicrania.

In M. Bulgakov's novel "THE MASTER AND MARGARITA", Mikhail Bulgakov is the greatest master who can sing the human soul from a variety of sides. Apparently, he, like Gogol, does not believe that the human soul is unable to rise, to be reborn, and this is clear from the example of the novel "The Master and Margarita", where the main characters gain immortality by rising from the dead, only Berlioz goes into oblivion. Bulgakov's main resurrectionist is Woland. Yes, he can resurrect a soul, and, conversely, destroy it.

In general, Woland in the novel appears to us as the devil on the contrary, because although his vocation is to destroy souls, he did it only with Berlioz and maybe with Maigel. Especially the resurrection of souls is vividly described at the ball. These people have long since died, and certainly not without the assistance of Woland himself, but every year, on a full moon, they gather for a ball, which is arranged by Woland, who resurrected them, probably because they believed in some philosophy, some theory.

Apparently, this theory was based on the idea of an afterlife, when the body dies and the soul remains alive. Woland, however, calls them proofs of a completely different theory. According to him, Berlioz all his life professed the theory that after cutting off the head, life the body ceases, and the soul goes into oblivion. It is quite obvious that the author's sympathies here are not on the side of Berlioz, however, not on the side of Woland either. Here M. Bulgakov puts forward the idea that everyone gets what they deserve, what they believed in, and you will

get it, as happened with Berlioz. Shower and, who gathered at this creepy ball, neighbors Volanda, they are in hell for their sins.

Most likely, Woland himself gradually suggested to them various ways of poisoning and other crimes. Every year new faces appear at this ball – Woland does not doze, he continues to kill souls. And he gathers them at the ball, of course, not in order to prove to Berlioz the correctness of his theory, in which he and his guests believe, but because in secret he is pleased to see the souls that he destroyed and then resurrected.

At first glance, it is not noticeable that these people suffer some kind of torment in hell, as sinners should, but even if this is the case, then perhaps Woland wants to give them a rest from their suffering. At least Frida, who is served a handkerchief every day to remind her of her crime, gets drunk, and it helps she forgot the ill-fated white with a blue border handkerchief. You come to completely different conclusions if you reflect on the immortality of Pilate.

Oddly enough, it turns out that his immortality is a kind of punishment. He had been sitting on his stone chair on the mountains for two thousand years and had the same dream for two thousand years – the torment could not be more terrible, especially since this dream is his most secret dream. He claims that he didn't finish something then, on the fourteenth month of Nissan, and wants to go back, go on the lunar road. He was freed from this torture by the Master, who flew away with Woland in search of peace to unknown distances. And how, then, did immortality come to Pilate? It came to him exactly on the day when Yeshua was executed. It all starts with hemicrania, a terrible disease in which it hurts, just a splitting headache. The procurator wanted to drink poison, but Yeshua cured him.

The procurator was fascinated by him and was even going to send him into exile, to his residence, but when he heard about the insult inflicted by the great of this world, he felt, if not horror, then fear. "Short, incoherent and quite extraordinary thoughts raced... "Perished?", then "Perished!", and some absolutely ridiculous among them about some kind of immortality, which must necessarily be, and immortality called unbearable longing." He felt it, realized that longing would disturb him later, but did not attach serious importance to his premonition at first. Immortality really came as soon as the procurator condemned Yeshua.

True, then it was still possible to change everything, to do something with the Sanhedrin, to arrange Yeshua's escape, finally, but as soon as the procurator heard for the third time that the Sanhedrin was freeing Barabbas, everything was over. He was again pierced by longing, and the thought of mysterious immortality made Pilate feel cold, feel the piercing cold in the sun. According to him, Yeshua was

leaving forever, because the procurator did not know that he would rise again, that he was immortal, and it turned out that with the condemnation of Yeshua, immortality, as it were, passed to Pilate. Pilate was henceforth doomed to eternal life, and if a person is doomed, then it does not bring anything good.

Although uninterrupted sleep on a stone throne cannot be called life, this existence is just that. Life began when "The Master cupped his hands and shouted: "Free!", and this is no longer doom, not unbearable longing, but the true joy of being together with Yeshua, who appears resurrected at the end of the book. Pilate's immortality ended in a moment, Woland says about this: "Why chase after what has already ended?" Pilate will continue to live on light, where the Master has not earned the right to life. The Master and Margarita are also a kind of people who have died and risen again. Azazello denies it, says that they are not dead, but at the same time Ivanushka's neighbor is dying, and Ivanushka finds out when the Master comes to say goodbye to him. It turns out that there are two Masters in the world: one who flew away with Woland, and the other who will die in the one hundred and eighteenth ward. And there are two Margaritas, too, although the epilogue says that the gang kidnapped both the Master and Margarita, and her housekeeper Natasha, turned into a witch. It was Azazello who prepared them for the flight with the help of Falernian wine, the same one that the procurator drank.

Already in this one can see a hint that the heroes of M. Bulgakov drink difficult wine. Yes, that's how it really turns out, because Azazello first poisons the Master and Margarita with his help, and then resurrects them. Obviously, you can't go on a flight with Woland alive; you need to prepare, put your own soul to sleep and forget yourself for a while. There is another resurrected person in the novel. This is Ivanushka, named in the epilogue by Ivan Nikolaevich Ponyrev. He was resurrected by the Master, but not from the dead, no, he is not so omnipotent for this – he has resurrected the soul, he is brought out of stagnation, from the apathy in which his soul was.

Suddenly he stopped writing incompetent poems, rejected vulgarity, became an educated person with a real living soul, and not with a piece of wax. And this is all the merit of the Master. In the end, I want to say something else: all these people have different souls, and they were resurrected in different ways and for different purposes. The guests at the ball gained immortality – to have fun, Berlioz – to go into oblivion, the Master and Margarita – to be able to fly with Woland to other distances, Pilate – got it for himself, and Ivanushka – just found himself. The writer seems to convince us, no matter what we are, with bad inclinations or noble in spirit, we can also become immortal and rise again. And it depends on us.

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